

INNOVATION ATTENDANCE MONITORING SYSTEM WITH HYGIENE DETECTION: AN AUTHENTICATED TEMPERATURE, MASK & FACE DETECTION TECHNIQUE USING MLX90614 AND OPENCV

Richa Saxena¹, Aishwarya Katyal², Jafri Al Ayaan³,
Jyotsana Bharti⁴, Muskan Agarwal⁵

¹Assistance Professor, CS&E Department, MIT, Moradabad
richasaxena2006@gmail.com

²B.Tech 4th Year, CS&E Department, MIT, Moradabad
aishukatyal9756@gmail.com

³B.Tech 4th Year, CS&E Department, MIT, Moradabad
ayaanjafri610@gmail.com

⁴B.Tech 4th Year, CS&E Department, MIT, Moradabad
jyotsanabharti18@gmail.com

⁵B.Tech 4th Year, CS&E Department, MIT, Moradabad
muskanagarwal1611@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

In the era of science and technology, technology and automation have been proven beneficial to us in many fields. Nowadays, people have a great concern for their health as the world is badly affected by COVID-19. The death ratio is increasing day by day and the WHO has made it incumbent to wear masks, but still many people are not ensuing the rules. The project consists of three variant modules that are connected to each other. The first module is IOT based and the Arduino Uno is the main device as all the other sensors like MLX90614 Infrared Temperature Sensor and Interface OLED Graphic Display are integrated with it, in this module we scan the temperature of the user entering an organization. The second module detects the mask with the help of Keras or TensorFlow techniques using a webcam. In the last module, we recognize the user by extracting the features of their face and matching them with one present in the database by verification and identification to mark their attendance with help of OpenCV or PCA technique. The system is very useful as it upholds in reducing human efforts and providing a safe environment for working.

KEYWORDS: *Arduino Uno, MLX90614 Infrared Temperature Sensor, Interface OLED Graphic Display, Webcam, Keras or TensorFlow, OpenCV or PCA*

1. Introduction

As we all know that the world has been affected by the deadly virus that is covid-19, which spreads with the interaction of one person to another. Many people have lost their life due to this deadly virus. As to avoid the risk of getting infected from this virus we have selected this paper. In this paper, we aim to make a system that could automatically monitor the temperature and mask of the particular person entering an organization, office, college, or school, etc. To protect ourselves from this virus, we all need to wear a mask and maintain social distance. At many organizations, we can see a person manually checking for the temperature with the help of a thermal screening gun. But checking temperature manually is not effective as it may lead to a life risk for the person who is checking. So, we aim to

Doi: [10.5281/zenodo.5211322](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5211322)

make a system with the help of sensors which could automatically examine the temperature of the person through his/her hand, and if the temperature is satisfactory the system reaches the next step which is mask detection. If the person is wearing a mask he/she could be allowed to enter the organization. To enhance the quality of the project we have introduced another module which is the face recognition attendance system. Most of the organizations have avoided the manual way of taking attendance and have introduced biometric^[10] devices. In biometric devices, we just need to register our thumbprint. But due to the coronavirus, it is not safe to use the biometric system for attendance marking. So, we have used the feature of face recognition to avoid the risk. As the person passes the temperature and mask check successfully the system then extracts the features of the person and matches it with the dataset provided. If the person matches, attendance is marked and the person can enter an organization successfully without making any trouble or risk to other's lives. This provides us a safe environment and can avoid manual work also.

2. Properties

- 1.This paper is to reduce the risk of getting infected due to the deadly coronavirus by providing a safe environment.
- 2.This paper removes the manual workload of detecting masks, monitoring temperature, and marking attendance.
- 3.This paper is scalable as we can add any new module can be added to the system.
- 4.Due to the increase in cases of covid-19 it is necessary to check the temperature and mask of every individual entering in organizations or colleges, for that we need to appoint a person, it can increase the life risk of that person too. So, this system can automatically monitor all things and provide a safe environment.
- 5.The temperature module is very important as even in day to day life having a high temperature can result in fever and can cause infection to others coming in contact.
6. The face detection system plays an important role in today's world as every organization, college or school, etc maintains the attendance of their workers or students. So, for this purpose having a manual system is not appropriate and in this phase of coronavirus, it is not possible to have a biometric system. So, face recognition is a better option.
- 7.This paper is also helping in time-saving as it automatically performs all tasks.

3. Hardware Used

3.1 Arduino Uno Board

Arduino Uno is an electronic device that supports both hardware and software. It is open-source and is considered to be the most typical micro-controller that can deal with the input chunk. For example, the sensors that can carry the realized data into the Arduino to get suitable decisions. Arduino micro-controller even deals with the output chunk and devices, for example, controlling lights, motors, and other actuators. The part which is accountable for controlling modules is supplied regularly on the board called ATMEGA that can be programmed easily using the Arduino IDE programming language. To create a programming user interface area to startup controlling tasks properly, we need to interface the board with a computer.^[1]

Figure 1. Arduino Uno

Voltage Divider :

$$V_{out} = V_{in} * (R_2 / (R_1 + R_2))$$

3.2 MLX90614 Infrared Temperature Sensor

The MLX90614 Infrared Temperature Sensor is used as a helpful tool. We will mainly utilize an MLX90614 Infrared Temperature Sensor to detect a person's temperature without any contact at all, and to also sense the surrounding temperature which is present near this sensor. The results will be displayed in both, degrees Fahrenheit and degrees Celsius on the serial monitor. Many real-world applications use an infrared temperature sensor to either be an aid for the user or autonomous monitoring, and some of those applications include body thermometers, fire detectors, water heaters, room heaters, etc.

Figure 2. MLX90614 Thermal Temperature Sensor

3.3 Interface OLED Graphic Display

OLED driver controller – SSD1306 can communicate with the micro-controller in multiple ways including I2C and SPI. OLED displays its own light that so it didn't need the background light. Due to the absence of background light, the power required to run the OLED reduces. The operating voltage of the SSD1306 controller is from 1.65V to 3.3V while the OLED panel requires 7V to 15V supply voltage. The OLED can be connected to Arduino without using any logic level converter. It uses 1000 memory area which is organized as- 8 pages (from 0 to 7) x 128 columns (block 0 to 127) x 8 bits of data (from 0 to 7) = 8192 bits = 1024 bytes = 1KB memory

Figure 3. OLED Graphic Display

The four libraries we used in OLED are – SPI.h, Wire.h, Adafruit_GFX.h and Adafruit_SSD1306.h

4. Software Used

4.1 Arduino Uno

Arduino Integrated Development Environment (IDE) is a multi-platform application that is used to write, upload, and compile the codes in Arduino Module working in C/C++. IDE is very easy to operate and can be used on Mac, Windows, and Linux platforms. There are many versions of Arduino such as Mega, Uno, Leonardo, Micro, etc.

4.2 DATABASE

In this, we will use the MYSQL or mongoose database to store the image of a person, and afterward we will use that image to detect and recognize the person entering the class to mark their attendance.

5. Working of Modules

5.1 Temperature Monitoring Through Thermal Screening Sensor

This module is kept keeping in mind the security issues due to coronavirus. There are 3 different sensors

- Thermal Screening
- Thermocouples
- Thermistor

In our module, we will use the Thermal Screening sensor^[2] to maintain a safe distance and avoid contact. In this module, we will detect the temperature of an individual with the help of the surrounding temperature.

5.1.1 Implementation of sensors

We will connect all sensors with Arduino which takes the input supply of 5 volts. We connect one wire to the supply and the other to the ground.

Figure 4. Circuit Diagram of Temperature Module

SD Chip module is used for processing all voices.

Connection –

- Black wires to OLED 128*64.
- Another black wire to GY-906.
- Brown to PAM8403.

SD Chip module connection with Arduino

- Red to SCK
- Green to SD
- Blue to IS
- Grey to CS

5.1.2 To complete this module we need to install some libraries

- Adafruit_MLX90614 library will be needed for the infrared thermometer.
- Adafruit_GFX is used to include the core graphics library for display.
- Adafruit_SSD1306 was used to drive the display.
- Fonts/FreeMonoBold18pt7b is used to add custom fonts.^[9]

Figure 5. Detecting temperature

5.2 Mask Detection Module

Due to pandemic COVID-19, Who has made it compulsory to wear masks to protect us against this deadly virus. So, in this module, we aim to build a Real-Time^[3] Face Mask Detector with python.^[4]

Software Required

1. Dataset - which consists of 1376 images with 690 images of people wearing masks and 686 images without masks. We too need a webcam to capture the image of a person.^[5]
2. Jupyter Notebook – in machine learning we require a jupyter notebook for development.

Hardware Required

1. Webcam – we need a webcam to capture the image of a person.

Libraries Required

1. OpenCV – OpenCV^[14] library is used for programming functions mainly aimed at real-time computer vision.
2. Keras - provides a Python interface for artificial neural networks and acts as an interface for the TensorFlow library.

The flow of the module will be constructed in parts–

5.2.1 Import

Firstly we will import all the libraries required for example-Import RMSprop, ImageDataGenerator, Cv2, etc. To successfully run our code.

5.2.2 Build Neutral Network

This convolution, network consists of two pairs of Conv and MaxPool to extract features from the dataset, which is further followed by the Flatten and Dropout layer to convert the data in 1D and ensure overfitting.

5.2.3 Image Data Generation

The new image is generated from the original ones by applying random jitters and perturbations.

5.2.4 Initialize

Initialize a callback checkpoint to keep saving the best model after each epoch while training.

Figure 6. Detection of Mask

In this module, if the user wears the mask (anything which covers the area from nose to chin) is allowed to enter the class or an organization otherwise no entry.

5.3 Face Recognition Attendance System

This system recognizes^[7] the person with the image saved in the database using the OpenCV or PCA Algorithm. It is constructed in 3 modules

- Image capturing
- Face Detection and
- Face recognition

The requirement for this module is a webcam and database along with libraries installed.

5.3.1 Image Capturing

As soon as the student enters the class the image is captured using the webcam and transferred to the server for processing. The image processing is checked with the one provided in the database. The camera will capture the image within limited dimensions, if the person is not present in between given dimensions, the image will not be captured.^[6]

5.3.2 Face Detection

As the image is captured the features of the person are extracted^[12] using the OpenCV^[5] or PCA Algorithm, the face is been detected in the database. There can be many factors that can interfere with the OpenCV or PCA Algorithm such as face pose, scale, position, rotation, light, image, color, etc.

5.3.3 Face Recognition

Recognizing a face means to identify that particular face from a list of faces in a database. As in face detection, there are many existing algorithms used to identify a face, but we are using OpenCV or PCA Algorithm^{[15][16]}. Our system implements a server-based module, programmed in Python which takes the benefit of eigenface to identify a face. This algorithm has many drawbacks: it depends on scales, poses, and the color of the compared images. However, the algorithm is very fast and can compare only two images, thus we do not need to have multiple images of a person to train our system.^[8]

Figure 7. Monitoring Face

The face detection system can also be understood as

Let a set of 'n' training images each with dimensions 'm*m'. Now, firstly convert those images into vectors with size 'm²'.

So, m*m images = m² * 1 vector

Let the images be a₁, a₂, a₃, a_n

Now, as we have obtained the vectors so, we will calculate the average of these face vectors –

$$\beta = 1/n (\sum a_i) \text{ -----(1)}$$

where, i = 1 to n

Now, we will subtract it from each vector

From equation (1) $y_i = a_i - \beta$ -----(2)

Now, we will take all the face vectors in the form of a matrix of size 'm²*n'

M = M^T with dimension 'n²*m'

$$C = M^T * M \text{ ----- (3)}$$

Now, using the formulas we will calculate the eigenvector and eigenvalues for the above matrix

$$M * M^T * M * u_i = \alpha_i * M^*$$

$$u_i C' * v_i = \alpha_i * v_i$$

Where, C' = M * M^T ----- (4)

$$v_i = A * u_i \text{----- (5)}$$

So, from equation (3) & (4) we can conclude that C' & C have some eigenvalue and eigenvectors which are related to each other with the help of equation (5)

Let, k = eigen vector for C' such that k < M(eigen value) with size 'm²'.

From equation (2) $a_i - \beta = \sum x_j * z_j$ -----(6)

where, j = 1 to k and z_j = eigenfaces

Let, b_i = normalized training faces

$$b_i = [x_1^i \ x_2^i \ x_3^i \ \dots \ x_k^i]$$

Let, c = unknown faces. So, $\rho = c - \beta$ -----(7)

Where, $\rho = \sum x_i * z_i$ -----(8)

$i = 1$ to k such that we project the normalized vector into eigen space.

For equation (8) the vector coefficient is

$$\Omega = [x_1 \ x_2 \ x_3 \ \dots \ x_k]$$

Now, to get the minimum distance between training vectors and testing vectors. where, e_r will be below the tolerance level, T_r

$$e_r = \min_l |\Omega - \Omega_l|$$

FLOW DIAGRAM OF MODULES

6. Conclusion

In the nutshell, I would like to conclude that with this growing phase in technology, we can use technology anywhere we want to, but we would like to take advantage of this technology in the field of health so that we could provide better habitat to everyone present around us. In this paper, we aim to provide covid-19 free conditions to everyone working in an organization or students studying in colleges or schools. The automatic system based on IOT and ML is very inviting as it brings down the physical effort of the people. In this paper, we have look over all the essentials conditions like temperature and mask which have been made mandatory by WHO, and along with that, we are

Doi: [10.5281/zenodo.5211322](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5211322)

automatically marking the attendance of the person, reducing the time lost in taking attendance manually. Through this paper, students can better understand the use of technology that is IOT and ML.

7. Future Scope

1. This paper holds use in the future as no end can be seen to this pandemic. As science and technology enhance this system can also be enhanced as per use.
2. Including an automatic sanitizer system can also be a good idea to be implemented in this paper. As sanitizing our hands is the major requirement of today's era. Except for this pandemic sanitization is important due to increasing infections and disease.
3. The automatic slip generator can also be added to this paper which can print the daily record of the person regarding his/her health in terms of temperature, which can help them maintain a safe distance, take right decisions, and maintain proper health.
4. This system could provide safety to the person doing all these works manually. We can use this system anywhere we want.

8. Challenges

1. Cost Within The range

As the sensors used in this paper are bit costly so the cost should be kept in range. So that many organizations and schools, etc can get benefited from this system.

2. Image capturing

As the image can be captured within certain dimensions, so if the person doesn't lie within the dimensions image cannot be captured.

3. Privacy

The data of the individual should be safe; there should be no misuse of data^[13].

4. Security

As the project contain the use of IOT sensors and laptop webcam the possibility of being hacked increases. The hacker can get control of devices and can create the problems^[11].

References

- [1]. Lal Bihari Barik, "IOT based Temperature and humidity controlling using Arduino and Raspberry Pi", (IJACSA) International Journal of Advanced Computer Science and Applications, Vol. 10, No. 9.
- [2]. G.C.M. Meijer, "Thermal Sensors based on Transistors", Sensors and Actuators, vol. 10, pp. 103-125, 1986.
- [3]. J. Martí, C. Ventura, J. Hollman, K. Srivastava and H. Juárez, "I2Sim Modelling and Simulation Framework for Scenario Development Training and Real-Time Decision Support of Multiple Interdependent Critical Infrastructures during Large Emergencies", NATO RTO Modelling and Simulation Group Conference, 2008.
- [4]. Shreyak Sawhney, Karan Kacker, Samyak Jain; Shailendra Narayan Singh; Rakesh Garg, "Real-Time Smart Attendance System using Face Recognition Techniques", 2019 9th International Conference on Cloud Computing, Data Science & Engineering (Confluence).
- [5]. Kruti Goyal, Kartikey Agarwal, Rishi Kumar, "Face detection and tracking: Using OpenCV", 2017 International conference of Electronics, Communication and Aerospace Technology (ICECA).
- [6]. P. Wagh, S. Patil, J. Chaudhari and R. Thakare, "Attendance System based on Face Recognition using Eigen face and PCA Algorithms", 2015 International Conference on Green Computing and Internet of Things (ICGCIoT), 2015.
- [7]. A. Jha, "Class Room Attendance System Using Facial Recognition System", International journal of Mathematical science technology and management, vol. 2, no. 3, pp. 2007, 2007.
- [8]. San Nyein Khine, Zaw Tun, "Sensor Analysis and Application of Arduino based Temperature and Light Intensity Control for Smart Home System", International Journal of Scientific and Research Publications, Volume 8, Issue 6, June 2018 89 ISSN 2250-3153.

- [9]. Soumya Dixit, Richa Saxena, Nayanika Singh, "Biometric Authentication Using Argyle Technique", MIT International Journal of Computer Science and Information Technology Vol.4, No. 2, August 2014, pp. 89-92 89 ISSN 2230-7621©MIT Publications.
- [10]. Richa Saxena, "A Novel Cryptography Based Digital Image Watermarking Scheme to Increase Security of Watermark Data Using Bit Replacement Technique", MIT International Journal of Computer Science and Information Technology, Vol. 6, No. 1, January 2016, pp. 48-52 48 ISSN 2230-7621©MIT Publications.
- [11]. Richa Saxena, Navita Agarwal, Prachi Agarwal, "Data Hiding and Extraction in Audio Files", MIT International Journal of Computer Science and Information Technology, Vol. 5, No. 2, August 2015, pp. 83-86 83 ISSN 2230-7621©MIT Publications.
- [12]. Richa Saxena, "Processing Secret Query using Blind Signature, Oblivious Transfer and Composite Protocol", MIT International Journal of Computer Science and Information Technology, Vol. 6, No. 1, January 2016, pp. 15-19 15 ISSN 2230-7621©MIT Publications.
- [13]. Prachi Agarwal, Navita Agarwal, Richa Saxena, "Data Encryption through Fibonacci Sequence and Unicode Character", MIT International Journal of Computer Science and Information Technology, Vol. 5, No. 2, August 2015, pp. 79-82 79 ISSN 2230-7621©MIT Publications.
- [14]. G. Bradski and A. Kaehler, "Learning c OpenCV", O'Reilly Media Inc., pp. 370-404, 2008.
- [15]. Priyanka Wagh, Roshani Thakare, Jagruti Chaudhari, Shweta Patil, "Attendance system based on face recognition using eigen face and PCA algorithms", 2015 International Conference on Green Computing and Internet of Things (ICGCIoT).
- [16]. K. Susheel Kumar, Shitala Prasad, Vijay Bhaskar Semwal and R. C. Tripathi, "Real Time Face Recognition using AdaBoost Improved Fast PCA Algorithm", IJAIA, vol. 2, no. 3, July 2011.

Authors

Richa Saxena received her M.Tech degree in Computer Science & Engineering in 2013 from TMU. She is currently an Assistant Professor in CSE Department at MIT with 13 years of professional experience. She has wide expertise in Cloud Computing with a strong background in Networking, Ethical Hacking, Python and has completed several STC's from NITTTR, Chandigarh.

Aishwarya Katyal is an undergraduate B.Tech student in Computer Science & Engineering from MIT and will graduate in 2021. She has great interest in Web Development including PHP & MYSQL. She has done training in Cloud Computing from NPTEL and in Core Java from NIIT. She is certified in Auto CAD and Maths Olympiad. She also has interest in other languages like C, C++ and Python.

Jafri Al Ayaan is an undergraduate B.Tech student in Computer Science & Engineering from MIT and will graduate in 2021. He has key interest in Competitive Coding with Python and has solved around 200 questions on GeeksforGeeks. He has participated in Code chef long challenge and has won 10th rank in his college.

Jyotsana Bharti is an undergraduate B.Tech student in Computer Science & Engineering from MIT and will graduate in 2021. She has interest area in Front End Development and UX&UI Designing. She is certified in cloud computing, IOT, and Robotics & Embedded System from CETPA and IIT Roorkee. She has knowledge regarding C, C++ and Java.

Muskan Agarwal is an undergraduate student in the Computer Science program at the MIT and will be graduating in 2021. She has a strong interest in the field in Data Science and Machine Learning. She has achieved 4th star grade on Hacker Rank in Python and has achieved proficiency in Data Science with Python certified and proficiency in Core Python certified by an organization named TCE Info Solutions Pvt Ltd.

